

[More](#)

Definition and Management of Metrics in Data Governance

Paulo R S Oliveira 12 min read · Jun 8, 2024

15

Photo by [fabio](#) on [Unsplash](#)

I. INTRODUCTION

We begin this article using the words of John Edwards [9], who is a veteran business technology journalist with several business and technology publications, who says: *“Today, every data transaction is a business transaction. That’s why it’s vital to build a data governance framework that is strong, secure,*

adaptable, and as error-free as possible. A critical mistake many IT leaders make is introducing data governance policies without ensuring that all important parts of the company have the tools and knowledge to implement them effectively.”

Data Governance (GD) has been a difficult area of business to work in. When everything is working and no noise is causing problems, your efforts go unnoticed. On the other hand, when problems arise and things go wrong, data governance is the first area to blame — *processes don't work, and you are not controlling it correctly!* Therefore, to demonstrate to shareholders [2] that the effort and investment made in GD are benefiting the business, reducing costs, and increasing revenue, it will be necessary to implement some metrics. This will allow the company to understand and see the improvement that is occurring.

But where to start and what to measure?

Photo by [Scott Graham](#) on [Unsplash](#)

To do so, we need to define ‘Data Governance Metrics’. In other words, we try to say something based on the determination of its uniqueness and describe what is specific and distinct about metrics, their meaning and their importance. So, the question immediately arises:

Why are metrics important?

Metrics are important because they can show whether or not there is alignment with business strategy and can *“help ensure that business process silos within the organization consistently understand and are aligned with governance program expectations”* says Kelle O’Neal [6], founder and CEO of First San Francisco Partners. *“Metrics can demonstrate the ongoing relevance and value of your data governance program.”* *“You will find that the definition of value, the definition of relevance, and how you align your organization changes over time; which means your metrics will also change over time,”* concludes O’Neal. Having established the importance of the metric, we now need to apply this understanding in the context of Data Governance.

What are metrics in Data Governance?

There is no doubt that data governance has brought new business and development opportunities. However, beyond having opportunities at hand, you need to understand, manage and measure them. That’s where Metrics Management in Data Governance comes in. The classic definition of metrics states that they are quantifiable measurements used to analyze the outcome of a specific process, action, or strategy. In other words, a metric is a number that represents the measure that you will monitor to understand what works (or not) in your work.

But can we only look at a metric as a quantitative measure?

The metric depends on what you want and need to measure. Among so many possibilities, to know which metrics are useful for your strategy, it is necessary to develop a plan.

John Ladley in his book 'Data Governance' [5] teaches us *“that we cannot manage what we do not measure”*. Over time, the Data Governance program will need to develop a way to monitor its effectiveness. Without it, the GD program will certainly disappear. Investigations show that metrics will be difficult to collect at first. After all, in the initial stage of the Data Governance program implementation process, there is no history or habit of data management, therefore, there is no 'infrastructure' to install a metric appropriately. But eventually, metrics will evolve from simple surveys and counts to true activity monitoring.

This is why Ladley teaches us that we must *“quantify the costs”*. He says that we need to *“examine current IT costs, as well as all other information-related costs. Also include all capital costs, depreciation, and overhead”*. In his talks, John Ladley also states that: *“any analysis of the cost of poor data quality must also be taken into account. Include the costs of departmental usage databases (silos), spreadsheets, and 'ShadowIT'. This is a good exercise to calculate the initial cost, as it shows how much is being spent now, without data governance”*. [5]

Being recognized as difficult, questions will necessarily arise such as:

How do you know if your efforts are working or if you are dragging your feet and getting nowhere?

Firstly, it is necessary to understand what the problems are, the objectives and the impacts of solving them.

Quoting Kelle O’Neal [6] again: *“Metrics are one of the hardest aspects of data governance [to understand] and also one of the most important,”* she said because metrics provide an opportunity to establish a baseline to *“know what bad data means and potentially what good data could mean”* creating a starting point for getting the organization as a whole to understand the need for better data. Metrics can help align an organization with a set of shared goals, *“and that alignment of expectations is really important.”* Metrics can also provide an opportunity to engage with stakeholders.

II. DISCUSSION

Experts and several authors argue that the first step to implementing any data governance process and related practices is to fully understand the people, processes, and tools that are currently used to maintain data. They say, we can’t fix what we don’t understand, so getting a solid picture of the data lifecycle in advance is critical.

Another important step is communication regarding the need and value proposition regarding Data Governance. It is necessary to obtain the right support throughout the organization. *“We did just that and secured executive and stakeholder support from the IT and business teams, which got us off to a great start”*, has been the testimony of those who have been successful in their businesses.

However, we need to agree with other authors that there is still something important missing to be added to the ‘menu’. It means we need to develop and publish meaningful metrics to show improvement and progress towards business objectives. Management at every company will want to see substantial evidence that their data governance initiative is positioned to succeed, so we need to make sure to establish a regular flow for sharing metrics and reports.

But, metrics should always refer to the underlying business objectives to demonstrate achievement against business value, and when necessary, refine the plan, analyze feedback, and clarify evolving business needs to maintain focus and the value proposition of Data Governance. In many instances, data initiatives have the ability to begin generating value during the initiative, well before completion, as any incremental improvements in data quality and availability can generate immediate insights to drive better decision-making.

We must also agree that failure to manage data is similar to failure to manage capital, and this results in waste and missed opportunities, as data not only represents value and opportunities, and when poorly managed, it also represents ethical and security risks. Security can cause misuse and loss of reliability, thus generating unreliability.

In this particular, an article by Suriya N Subramanian [1], mentions in his post on LinkedIn, that some simple metrics help for the success of Data Governance. Therefore, we highlight, in a reduced form, that the way to show the progress of successful data governance is through monitoring some key indicators, such as:

- i) Improvement in Data Quality Indices
- ii) Adherence to Data Management Standards and Processes
- iii) Reduction of risk events
- iv) Reduction in data rectification costs

Nevertheless, we need to mention that nowadays a company's management must realize that there is progress towards a set of metrics that can be measured, as well as the impact of this progress on the organization. Several

authors also mention that this progress can be measured in four contexts: people, processes, technology, and data.

a) Progress metrics: people

When implementing a data governance program, there are ways to measure progress as it relates to people, such as:

1. tasks and activities that involve alignment
2. designation and integration of people as part of the program
3. the number of people who have been trained and their continued participation
4. tracking the number of resolved issues
5. the number of approved projects

b) Measures of progress: processes

Experts in the field argue that measuring processes is a great way to measure how well governance is embedded in the organization, including:

1. identify which processes have an impact on your objectives and focus your measurement on them
2. identify and articulate how processes are created
3. how implementation planning should occur

4. how the processes will be executed
5. Do people understand what the new process is?
6. Are people using the new process?
7. are we working with our backlog of processes?

c) Measures of progress: technology

Investigators of the progress of technology planning and implementation within the Data Governance program state that:

1. Progress can be measured by data integrity between systems,
2. by the number of consolidated data sources,
3. by the number of data targets using metadata

d) Progress metrics: data

Authors specializing in the field of Data Governance and several researchers agree that options for measuring progress with data may include analyzing common data entities and how improvement requests for these data entities are managed or documenting these data entities, because perhaps in this analysis we are looking at the efficiency of the process.

However, despite having mentioned a wide range of metrics in the four items above, this range does not exhaust what analysts, researchers, authors,

and specialists usually highlight in their works, articles, and interviews. [2]
[3][4]

We don't even need to mention that we're swimming in metrics, right?

Photo by [Mikail McVerry](#) on [Unsplash](#)

It would take a lot of effort to address all the feedback to address all of them.
We believe we should reduce it, as a provocation for future debate, and

perhaps we should focus on the metrics of:

- Data Accuracy
- Cost Reduction
- Number and frequency of audit visits

III. CRITICAL ANALYSIS

As the number of IT metrics multiplies, it's important to focus on key indicators that offer at-a-glance insight into essential business functions.

Evidently, metrics are essential tools that help an organization's management focus its teams and resources on important core business areas, such as transformation and operations. However, while highly useful, metrics can also be dangerous when used inappropriately.

Photo by [Road Trip with Raj](#) on [Unsplash](#)

It's easy, for example, to rely on the wrong metric to track a specific trade, a mistake that can lead to inaccurate or misleading results. Complicating matters is the constant stream of new metrics, many of which have yet to prove their value over the long term.

Numbers say many things, but they do not show everything. It is necessary to look beyond the numbers to understand and understand what is really happening. Many experts argue that when putting together a package of metrics that can be used to capture the impact of Data Governance on transformations and operations, their minimalism should be fundamental.

Avoiding clutter and confusion to instead focus on a core set of fundamental metrics that provide a clear view of critical issues and challenges. And while additional analysis tools can be added over time to augment and illuminate important trends, it's best to start with just a few basic tools.

Matt Mead, CTO at technology consulting firm SPR [8], believes IT and business team engagement is a powerful metric for measuring success.

“We know that teams undergo psychological development through training, confrontation, standardization, and performance”, he says. “We also know that it takes time for joint technical and business teams, typically created for an organizational transformation, to solidify and mesh”. Mead notes that he often sees clients failing to allocate enough time for changes to take hold. Instead, under-engaged business and IT project leaders declare success and move prematurely to the next stage.

*“The best metric, especially during the first year, is to measure the **engagement** level of all team business and IT team members,”* he advises.

“If engagement is high, you have the foundation to be successful,” says Mead.

“If engagement is low, failure is likely.”

Therefore, we need to discover one or more characteristics of what is being measured. So, we need to understand that the result of an indicator is feedback. **Not every result is a number, but every indicator is a result.** Thus, it provides information about what has already happened (or what should have happened). Thus, understanding feedback is related both to understanding what happened and whether it occurred efficiently or not during the process.

Take for example semi-annual metrics. This does not mean that we should only check the metric after six months. We can do monthly or bi-weekly checks to get feedback on what has already happened and make corrections [7].

These fixes may seem superficial, even because it is an immediate action. However, we need to evolve to an understanding of feedback when we look at the number of times it was necessary to adjust and why this number of corrections occurred. Feedback helps to align and correct, but understanding helps to promote change. Changes are different from adjustments. Understanding the accumulation of adjustments requires a deep analysis of the causes, as we may be faced with situations that concern the gain or loss of company value that Data Governance and its Metrics may cause, despite all the concerns we may take, or no matter how technical the implementation of Data Governance in the company was.

IV. CONCLUSION

As we mentioned in the introduction to this article, and after having highlighted above the importance (and in a certain way the exaggerated quantity) of metrics in Data Governance, we want to mention as part of our conclusion, what Kelle O’Neal, founder and CEO of First San Francisco Partners, presented at DATAVERSITY® Enterprise Data Governance Online 2017. She said, “*When it comes to metrics, less is more.*”

We highlight that investors, creditors, shareholders, and society in general end up bearing some losses generated in organizations, and although the metrics deal with past events, our concern with the organization must consider the future, as the past is only history, relevant history, but just history.

It is in the future that the risk of poorly established, poorly managed, and poorly evaluated metrics lies, since the establishment, management, and evaluation are carried out by people, hence the need to involve interested parties becomes super important.

As Peter Drucker taught us, the “first function” of a manager, Drucker said: *“is people. It’s the relationship with people, the development of mutual trust. . . the creation of a community.”* Or, as Albert Einstein observed: *“Not everything that can be counted counts, and not everything that counts can be counted.”*[11].

This way, we want to highlight the importance of the need to obtain **engagement** in the establishment and management of GD metrics, as without the proper coverage of the entire organization, there will be no point in starting and defining the correct scope of the metrics if they are ‘forgotten’ on the organization’s bulletin board.

Photo by [Austin Distel](#) on [Unsplash](#)

So I turn again to Kelle O’Neal, who teaches us that we don’t need to measure everything, she says: *“You just need to choose what is important and meaningful to your stakeholder group and your program”*.

Therefore, when reflecting on mutual trust, engagement and stakeholders, it is almost impossible not to end our article by mentioning the spectacular phrase by Sheryl Sandberg, former COO of Facebook, who said:

“Speaking can transform minds, which can transform behaviors, which can transform institutions.”

References:

[1] Suriya N Subramanian, Simple Metrics for a Successful Data Governance

available online: <https://www.linkedin.com/pulse/simple-metrics-successful-data-governance-suriya-n-subramanian-fcca/>

[2] DAMA — DMBOK — 2nd Edition(2017)

[3] liz henderson, Treading Water in Your Data Efforts?

available on line:

<https://lizhendersondata.wordpress.com/2015/10/26/treading-water-in-your-data-efforts/>

[4] 35 Metrics You Should Use to Monitor Data Governance

available online: <https://dataflog.com/read/35-metrics-monitor-data-governance/1601>

[5] John Ladley, DATA GOVERNANCE – How to Design, Deploy, and Sustain an Effective Data Governance Program (2012), Elsevier Inc.

[6] Data Governance Program Effectiveness by the Numbers, By Amber Lee Dennis on September 6, 2017

available online: <https://www.dataversity.net/data-governance-program-effectiveness-numbers/>

[7] Monise Carla, O que é análise crítica de indicadores?

available online: <https://blogdaqualidade.com.br/o-que-e-analise-critica-de-indicadores/>

[8] Articles by Matt Mead, Matt Mead is the Chief Technology Officer at SPR Consulting.

available online: <https://spr.com/author/matt/>

[9] Articles by John Edwards

Available online: <https://www.cio.com/article/3639530/7-data-governance-mistakes-to-avoid.html>

[10] <https://kalendae.com.br/blog/cobit-gerenciamento-da-ti/>

<https://kalendae.com.br/blog/cobit-2019/>

[11] John Doerr, Measure What Matters (2018), Portfolio/Penguin

Data Governance

Engagement

Metrics And Analytics

Data Analysis

Data Science

Written by Paulo R S Oliveira

Edit profile

17 followers · 102 following

Lifelong Learner. Quite excited to learn more and more about regression, time series analysis, and forecasting models.

No responses yet

Paulo R S Oliveira

What are your thoughts?

More from Paulo R S Oliveira

 Paulo R S Oliveira

Stock Market Analysis

Could the stock price be predicted just by graphical visualization made by ML models?

Jun 8, 2024 1

 Paulo R S Oliveira

Heart Disease—Multivariate Analysis with R (Part 1 of 3)

Factor Analysis—Cluster Analysis—Discriminant Analysis

★ Jun 18, 2024 20

Recommended from Medium

:2510.01171v3 [cs.CL] 10 Oct 2025

ABSTRACT

Post-training alignment often reduces LLM diversity, leading to a phenomenon known as *mode collapse*. Unlike prior work that attributes this effect to algorithmic limitations, we identify a fundamental, pervasive data-level driver: *typicality bias* in preference data, whereby annotators systematically favor familiar text as a result of well-established findings in cognitive psychology. We formalize this bias theoretically, verify it on preference datasets empirically, and show that it plays a central role in mode collapse. Motivated by this analysis, we introduce *Verbalized Sampling (VS)*, a simple, training-free prompting strategy to circumvent mode collapse. VS prompts the model to verbalize a probability distribution over a set of responses (e.g., "Generate 5 jokes about coffee and their corresponding probabilities"). Comprehensive experiments show that VS significantly improves performance across creative writing (poems, stories, jokes), dialogue simulation, open-ended QA, and synthetic data generation, without sacrificing factual accuracy and safety. For instance, in creative writing, VS increases diversity by 1.6-2.1x over direct prompting. We further observe an emergent trend that more capable models benefit more from VS. In sum, our work provides a new data-centric perspective on mode collapse and a practical inference-time remedy that helps unlock pre-trained generative diversity.

Problem: Typicality Bias Causes Mode Collapse

Tell me a joke about coffee.

Solution: Verbalized Sampling (VS) Mitigates Mode Collapse

Different prompts collapse to different modes:

In Generative AI by Adham Khaled

Stanford Just Killed Prompt Engineering With 8 Words (And I...

ChatGPT keeps giving you the same boring response? This new technique unlocks 2x...

★ Oct 20, 2025 🖱️ 25K 💬 683 🗨️ ...

In itiversity by Sarath Sagi

Data Engineering System Design: Clickstream Data Into a Modern...

A complete end-to-end architecture for building scalable clickstream analytics and...

Dec 11, 2025 🖱️ 67 💬 2 🗨️ ...

 In Write A Catalyst by Dr. Patricia Schmidt

As a Neuroscientist, I Quit These 5 Morning Habits That Destroy You...

Most people do #1 within 10 minutes of waking (and it sabotages your entire day)

★ Jan 14

 In Level Up Coding by Kusireddy

I Stopped Using ChatGPT for 30 Days. What Happened to My Brai...

91% of you will abandon 2026 resolutions by January 10th. Here's how to be in the 9% who...

 In Data Engineer Things by Clay Gambetti

8 Hours to Clarity: Understanding dbt

A beginner's deep dive into the data build tool transforming modern analytics

★ Nov 24, 2025

 Netflix Technology Blog

Data as a Product: Applying a Product Mindset to Data at Netflix

Introduction: What if we treated data with the same care and intentionality as a consumer...

★ Dec 28, 2025

👏 12K

💬 442

Oct 7, 2025

👏 890

💬 28

See more recommendations

[Help](#)

[Status](#)

[About](#)

[Careers](#)

[Press](#)

[Blog](#)

[Privacy](#)

[Rules](#)

[Terms](#)

[Text to speech](#)